

ISic3661

I.Sicily inscription 3661

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

aedicula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lilybaeum

Place of origin (modern)

Marsala

Provenance

excavation 1974, via del Fante, proprieta Rallo Lidia

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Antonino Salinas, inventory 24363

Physical Description**Dimensions**

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout**Execution**

Engraved

Letter Forms**Letter heights:**

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR108287

1. [---]spex

Apparatus**Translation****Commentary****Digital identifiers:**

EDR 108287

Bibliography

Di Stefano, C.A. 1984. Lilibeo. Testimonianze archeologiche dal IV sec a.C. al V sec. d.C.. Palermo. At 171-173 no.189 fig.93

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